

Towards an LLM-Powered Expert System for AAS-based Product Digital Twin Development

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Abstract—Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS) is emerging as a cornerstone of Industry 4.0 and 5.0, enabling production requesters and providers to orchestrate manufacturing and supply chain processes as interoperable digital services. At the core of this paradigm are Product Digital Twins (PDTs), which extend beyond virtual representations of physical assets to encompass the entire product lifecycle—from design and configuration to maintenance, recycling, and sustainability compliance. In this context, accurate PDT design requires both deep product understanding and systematic integration of diverse information models, such as bill of materials, bill of services, and including Digital Product Passports (DPP) for circularity and regulatory authorities. This paper presents an initial conceptual approach to a Large Language Model (LLM)-powered expert system engineered to support Asset Administration Shell (AAS)-based PDT development within a MaaS ecosystem. It illustrates how an LLM-powered technology can support and augment domain experts and system engineers in collaboratively creating, refining, and deploying PDTs, thereby contributing to global manufacturing resilience.

Index Terms—Large Language Model, Expert Systems, Supply Chain Management, MaaS, Asset Administration Shell

I. INTRODUCTION

The product is undeniably a central motivation behind manufacturing and the supply chain. Indeed, while manufacturing focuses on transforming raw materials into finished products, the supply chain also encompasses other activities such as logistics and retailing to ensure that products reach the hands of customers. In the current manufacturing ecosystem (Industry 4.0 and 5.0), the product remains at the core, but manufacturing and the supply chain are now subject to new requirements concerning flexibility, automation, human-centricity, sustainability, and resilience [1]. Such new context requires each product to be associated with additional information beyond its basic characteristics, such as carbon footprint, traceability, and maintenance details.

Product Digital Twin (PDT) is a specific type of digital twin that is dedicated to represent a product. It is defined as the “collection of all information related to a product, including ones of the Digital Product Passport” [2]. In some cases, this term can be used interchangeably with Digital Product Passport (DPP), which refers to “the collection of all product information relevant for circularity and regulatory authorities”. Both PDT and DPP represent two related but distinct concepts for managing the product information. The PDT

offers a comprehensive, technology-agnostic digital representation of a product throughout its entire lifecycle, supporting functions such as analytics, optimization and maintenance. By comparison, the DPP has a more narrowly defined scope, primarily focused on data elements mandated by European Union regulations to ensure circularity, traceability, and regulatory compliance [3]. In current industrial applications, a convergence is occurring where the DPP is increasingly treated as an integral component within the broader PDT architecture. This integration facilitates the alignment of operational data, lifecycle modeling, and regulatory disclosure requirements.

PDT is particularly critical in emerging production paradigms like Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS), where manufacturing and supply chain processes are delivered as discrete services. MaaS demands significant transparency and accessibility of product information to ensure data consistency and reliability across different service providers. However, designing a robust PDT information model presents challenges. While standardized vocabularies such as the Asset Administration Shell (AAS¹) and ECLASS² provide foundational support, the high variability of modern products requires designers to look beyond the product’s immediate characteristics. They must also account for the diverse informational needs of all stakeholders and services throughout the product’s lifecycle.

One way to support PDT designers is using expert systems. Since the introduction of R1 (or XCON), the first commercial expert system applied in manufacturing in the early 1980s, expert systems have consistently shown their value in industrial contexts. This system is highly reliable because its knowledge base (consisting of a fact base and a rule base) is built on the knowledge of domain experts, and every decision is derived strictly through logical reasoning [4]. However, building an expert system can be costly and heavily depends on the role of knowledge engineers, who, in theory, must perform multiple tasks: extracting knowledge from domain experts, translating facts and rules into languages understandable by the machine, implementing and maintaining the expert system throughout its operational life [5]. To address this issue, our research work in context of the ongoing Horizon Europe-funded project

¹<https://industrialdigitaltwin.org/en/content-hub/aasspecifications>

²<https://eclass.eu/en/>

RAASCEMAN³ (2024-2027) proposes a new approach for developing expert systems by leveraging Large Language Models (LLMs). The LLM handles not only natural language understanding (NLU) and natural language generation (NLG), but also reasoning, making it a promising candidate for implementing an expert system. The key novelty is that the approach can reduce the dependence on the very specific role of a "Knowledge Engineer" and allows other project members, such as system engineers and domain experts, to contribute to this LLM-powered Expert System (LLM-ExSys) directly.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II provides the background information, including the concepts of AAS and LLM-powered techniques. Next, Section III presents the case study and practical context involving this research. Section IV focuses on the main contributions, which are a method and experiences to deploy an LLM-ExSys for PDT deployment. Section V discusses the limitations. Finally, a conclusion sums up this paper and outlines future work.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Asset Administration Shell (AAS)

AAS is a standard for digital twins, originally introduced by Plattform Industrie 4.0 and further developed by the Industrial Digital Twin Association (IDTA). The AAS information model of a digital twin serves as a digital representation of a physical or digital asset and is structured into submodels, each describing a specific aspect of the asset. To specify an aspect in more detail, submodel elements such as properties and collections are added to the corresponding submodel. The submodels provide a standardized means to organize and manage asset-related information in a consistent and interoperable manner.

By defining common standardized interfaces, the AAS standard facilitates interoperability among heterogeneous assets and enables seamless data exchange between physical and virtual entities. Interactions are realized through standardized communication mechanisms, supporting integration within Industry 4.0 environments. Several implementations of the AAS standard have been proposed, including the Eclipse AASX Package Explorer and Papyrus4Manufacturing as tools for designing AAS information models, as well as the FA³ST and Eclipse BaSyx reference frameworks for the deployment and management of digital twins.

B. Large Language Model (LLM)-Powered Techniques

LLMs are a type of artificial intelligence (AI) system that learn statistical patterns from massive amounts of text data to support processing and generating human-understandable language. LLMs have achieved impressive capabilities in diverse natural language tasks, but still exhibit important limitations, such as hallucinations, restricted context windows, and outdated parametric knowledge. Recent research explores several techniques to enhance LLM performance and reliability.

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) techniques improve LLMs by connecting them to external information

sources, including document repositories and knowledge bases [6]. During inference, relevant data is retrieved and integrated into the model's input context, providing an additional factual foundation that helps the LLM generate more accurate and contextually coherent responses. Using external knowledge in this way, these methods reduce the risk of hallucinated output and provide up-to-date answers based on recent data.

Tool-augmented LLM techniques extend the capabilities of an LLM by enabling dynamic interaction with external software tools, such as calculators, search engines, and code execution environments. This approach transitions the model from purely parametric reasoning to a hybrid paradigm, in which the LLM orchestrates and delegates tasks to the suitable tools. Although many studies show its effectiveness in structured reasoning and precise computation [7], this paradigm also introduces new challenges, including optimal tool selection, dependency resolution, and cost-efficient execution.

Prompt Engineering techniques are about designing and structuring inputs for an LLM to effectively guide its reasoning processes, thereby providing more accurate and relevant responses [8]. Some typical strategies are zero-shot prompting, few-shot prompting and chain-of-thought (CoT) prompting. Zero-shot prompting involves providing all necessary context, constraints, and instructions in a single prompt, without requiring any examples. Few-shot prompting guides the model's behavior by including a small number of labeled input-output examples within the prompt. CoT prompting demands the model to generate explicit intermediate reasoning steps before producing the final answer. Self-consistency methods further improve the robustness of CoT prompting by sampling diverse reasoning paths and aggregating the most consistent response, mitigating the limitations of single-step heuristics. Although these strategies offer cost-effective and adaptable solutions, their effectiveness is sensitive to prompt formulation, as minor modifications can yield substantial variations in model output.

Verification techniques are combined with **human-in-the-loop (HITL)** strategies to improve the reliability of LLMs. Thus, LLM outputs can be systematically evaluated partly by human experts before being accepted. Some common components in this verification pipelines are automated fact-checking, confidence calibration, auxiliary re-ranking, and expert review. Besides identifying inaccuracies and improving factual correctness, human reviewers can also recheck and enforce ethical and operational constraints. HITL frameworks, such as InstructGPT [9], are particularly critical in high-stakes or domain-specific applications. However, it can become costly if the implementation is not optimized.

Fine-tuning is a technique for adapting a foundation LLM by re-training it with data from a specific domain, process and task. The fine-tuned LLM can be more accurate and richer to the target domain. Several parameter-efficient methods are widely used and deliver strong performance, such as Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) and adapter tuning [10]. The fine-tuning can also become costly, as it requires high-quality datasets and significant computational capabilities.

³<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101138782>

III. CASE STUDY: RAASCEMAN PROJECT

The Horizon Europe-funded project called Resilient and Adaptive Supply Chains for Capability-based Manufacturing as a Service Networks (**RAASCEMAN**⁴) is a collaborative project of nine research and industrial partners from six European countries. Technically, the project aims to leverage the latest concepts and technologies from Industry 4.0 and 5.0 to represent the supply chain as a network of services following the MaaS production paradigm.

PDT is defined as one of the conceptual cornerstones of RAASCEMAN, and the information it conveys is required by most of the applications and services involved in the project. The project focuses on only two types of products (1) electric bikes and (2) automobiles; however, the future aim of the RAASCEMAN solution is to provide high-quality production prototypes that work with other product types.

For interoperability, RAASCEMAN adopts the AAS standard as the core for modeling the information models of PDTs. An AAS-based PDT is composed of AAS submodels, wherein each represents an aspect of the product. These submodels can be standardized by using templates available in the IDTA hub⁵ or customized for specific needs of the end user. To support collective development and usage of PDT information models, the project applied a two-flow approach [11]: AAS submodel template design flow and AAS submodel instance deployment flow. Figure 1 illustrates a simplified version of the approach. In the first step, a group of project members working as AAS submodel template designers analyzes application requirements, designs templates, and publishes them on the cloud for shared use. In the second step, PDT instance designers can download templates appropriate to their use case from the cloud. In the third step, they modify and combine templates to form a complete PDT information model, then populate it with real data.

Figure 1. Steps to create a PDT instance in RAASCEMAN

However, a challenge arises: as the number of AAS submodel templates grows, PDT instance designers may struggle to find and evaluate them all, potentially increasing design costs. Therefore, an expert system is needed to assist in

⁴<https://raasceman.eu/>

⁵<https://industrialdigitaltwin.org/en/content-hub/submodels>

querying information and selecting suitable templates. At the early stage of the project, four basic functionalities are defined: (1) to provide a list of submodel templates that contain a specific property, (2) to provide a list of submodel templates associated with a specific product, (3) to provide a list of submodel templates required by a RAASCEMAN application or service, and (4) to suggest properties for products which are not predefined in the project.

IV. AN LLM-POWERED EXPERT SYSTEM FOR AAS SUBMODEL TEMPLATE RECOMMENDATION

This section first introduces the general method of LLM-ExSys, then presents a sample system implementation from the RAASCEMAN case study to support PDT development. The third subsection provides an early-stage experiment and discusses results.

A. Method

Figure 2 illustrates the main components of the LLM-ExSys. Similar to other expert systems, it is composed of a knowledge base, including a rule base and a fact base, and an inference engine. The user interface is another module that facilitates interaction between the system and its users. The core difference relies on three points:

- The facts in fact base and rules in rules base are stored and represented in human-readable format.
- The inference engine is actually an LLM model that performs logical reasoning, similar to any traditional inference engine. This component is referred to as the LLM-powered inference engine. It can either be an LLM running locally within the LLM-ExSys or an external LLM service that communicates with the LLM-ExSys through an Application Programming Interface (API) provided by the LLM service.
- The reasoning process occurs through the prompt engineering *zero-shot* technique, in which facts and rules are inserted into a prompt template as context. Moreover, one or more instructions can be included into the prompt template to guide the LLM in configuring the reasoning task and defining the expected output. When a new query is injected, the prompt content is sent to the LLM to perform reasoning.

In the LLM-ExSys architecture, the tasks of knowledge acquisition and engineering can be simplified and automated by leveraging an LLM, as it is effective at analyzing natural language. The role of knowledge engineers is reduced and, in some cases, can even be omitted. It allows domain experts to directly inject new facts and rules into the fact base and rule base using natural language or any formats supported by the system. Figure 3 illustrates the algorithm that LLM-ExSys process facts and rules as the input. In detail, the system waits for input. When an input is arrived, the system validates both the input format and the conveyed data content. If an unsupported format or any abnormal content is detected, the data is discarded; otherwise, the system converts the input into natural language and applies techniques to clean the data. Data

Figure 2. Major components of the LLM-ExSys

cleaning may involve multiple sub-tasks, such as breaking complex paragraphs into simpler ones, translating text between languages, or adding and removing words. The texts after cleaning become facts or rules, then being inserted into the fact base or rule base correspondingly. The LLM-ExSys repeats this process throughout its operational life.

Figure 3. Main steps in the facts and rules injection

Unlike fact and rule injection, instruction injection is simpler. The system engineer, who builds the whole system and is responsible for the system, can directly add or remove instructions in the LLM-powered inference engine with or without any validation or data cleaning. Note that a system engineer is different from a knowledge engineer, as the former may have little or no knowledge of the application domain.

B. System Implementation

In RAASCEMAN, the LLM-ExSys consists of a backend system module called the AAS Model Lake (AASML). It provides three major features: (1) storing and managing AAS submodel templates created by AAS submodel template designers, (2) distributing these templates to PDT instance designers, and (3) assisting PDT instance designers in selecting appropriate templates for their use case. AASML provides an API that enables any frontend to use these features. Overall, there are four actors involved in the LLM-ExSys:

- **AAS submodel template designers** act as domain experts who provide facts to the fact base. Technically, they upload AAS submodel templates in JSON or XML format to the LLM-ExSys. While templates in JSON format are created using the AASX Package Explorer⁶, those in XML format are created using the Papyrus4Manufacturing⁷. These templates are then validated and transformed into YAML format before being stored in the fact base. Note that YAML format is more human-readable than JSON and XML, thus it is easier for an LLM to analyze the content.
- **Group of manufacturing experts** serve as domain experts. They input their requirements using natural language, which can then be translated into rules. In practice, some members of RAASCEMAN manually perform the steps of validating and translating the requirements into rules. For example, let us take a requirement from the public deliverable report D1.1 RAASCEMAN Requirements and specifications⁸: “PDT data should be updated with data (e.g., carbon footprint, environmental and health impact) from the recommendation engine” is validated and translated into “If an entity is PDT, then it includes Carbon Footprint, Environmental Impact, and Health Impact”. In another example, the requirement “Steps to produce the product” is validated and translated into “If an entity is PDT, then it includes Bill of Services”. While the first example shows no need for a knowledge engineer, as the task is simply about reorganizing and reformulating the original sentence of the manufacturing expert, the second case requires a knowledge engineer who knows that the steps to produce a product is actually part of the Bill of Services submodel. The rules are stored in the rule base.
- **PDT instance designers** play the role of users who send queries to the LLM-ExSys. If a query falls outside the scope of the four functions presented in Section III, no answer will be provided.
- **System engineers** not only build the LLM-ExSys, but also configure its instructions. The following is a sample instruction that demands LLM to work as a reasoner: “Based on the rules and facts, perform reasoning to identify which submodels or properties are required for the given query”.

Figure 4 illustrates the complete prompt template constructed and used in the LLM-ExSys based on the user input. The four keywords **User Query**, **Rules**, **Facts**, and **Instruction** are unchanged, but their contents can be updated over time. In detail, every received query triggers the system to retrieve data from fact base and rule base. Thus, if any new rules or facts are added at a given moment, the next trigger will include them for reasoning.

At the time of writing this paper, our system has 416 facts

⁶<https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/dt.aaspe>

⁷<https://eclipse.dev/papyrus/components/manufacturing/>

⁸<https://zenodo.org/records/16780374>

Figure 4. Prompt template used in the LLM-ExSys in RAASCEMAN

and 50 rules in total. Note that the 416 facts are extracted from 55 AAS submodel templates⁹. Without any special instruction, LLM-ExSys works correctly against the first three functions presented in Section III, using Gemini 2.5 Flash¹⁰ as the LLM service. The fourth function is tricky, as it requires the LLM-ExSys to have information beyond the available facts. At this point, the generative-AI feature of LLM can be used to suggest additional properties in applying this instruction: "If the query contains the keyword 'create' and refers to creating characteristics for a new product not present in the facts, then add properties related to the new product to the 'Characteristics' submodel, and return the resulting list of properties". Note that, even the instruction is in the form of IF-THEN, it differs from a rule. While a rule affects the existing facts, the instruction influences the operation of the LLM-powered inference engine.

C. Experimentation and Evaluation

To evaluate the LLM-ExSys, four requests are prepared corresponding to the four required functions presented in Section III:

- 1) Give submodels that have the speed property
- 2) Give submodels for a car product
- 3) Give submodels required by the decision support tool
- 4) Create properties for a pen product

It is worth noting that the car is a type of automobile product, and speed is a property associated with vehicles, related both the electric bike and the automobile (two pre-defined products in RAASCEMAN). The decision support tool is an application within the project. The pen, as the only excluded product, is unrelated to the project.

First, the four requests are posed to the domain experts, and their answers are recorded in an Excel file. These answers will later be used to validate the outputs of the LLM-ExSys. The same four requests are also provided as input to the LLM-ExSys, and each is executed 10 times.

⁹<https://raasceman.pkgi40.codelib.re/modelake>

¹⁰<https://cloud.google.com/vertex-ai/generative-ai/docs/models/gemini/2-5-flash>

As a result, the outputs of the first three requests, as shown in Figure 5, match the answers provided by the domain experts, and are deterministic across 10 tests. However, the outputs for the fourth request are non-deterministic, as shown in Figure 6. For instance, in the left image, we can see seven new properties to the Characteristics submodel, while in the right image nine. The reason for this difference is that the answers to the first three requests are constrained by the fact and rule bases, and therefore result from logical deduction. The fourth request, on the other hand, requires an answer with information generated by the LLM, and the LLMs themselves are non-deterministic.

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Answer:
- ElectricBikeCharacteristics
- AutomotiveCharacteristics
.....
Ask your question: give me submodels for a car product
Answer:
- AutomotiveCharacteristics
- Maintenance
- OperationalInstructions
- BillOfMaterial
- Nameplate
- CarbonFootprint
- HealthImpact
- EnvironmentalImpact
- Usage
- Traceability
- BillOfServices
- Quality
- CommercialInformation
- AssetLocation
.....
Ask your question: give me submodels required by the decision support tool
Answer:
- BillOfServices
- BillOfMaterial
.....

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Figure 5. Deterministic outputs of the first three questions

<pre> Ask your question: create me p roperties for a pen product Answer: - Length - Width - Height - Diameter - Weight - Volumn - Material - Surface - Color - LengthUnit - WidthUnit - HeightUnit - DiameterUnit - WeightUnit - VolumnUnit - Ink Color - Pen Type - Tip Size - Refillable - Retractable - Grip Type - Cap Type </pre>	<pre> Ask your question: create me p roperties for a pen product Answer: - Length - Width - Height - Diameter - Weight - Volumn - Material - Surface - Color - LengthUnit - WidthUnit - HeightUnit - DiameterUnit - WeightUnit - VolumnUnit - InkType - TipSize - BarrelMaterial - CapType - Refillable - InkColor - WritingMechanism - GripMaterial - ClipMaterial </pre>
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Figure 6. Non-deterministic outputs of the fourth question

Another technical problem to discuss is the use of the Google Gemini 2.5 Flash free tier for testing. It raises two main issues: (1) data privacy concerns, (2) performance issues. For instance, during our experimentation we observed that

even though the number of tokens were relatively small (about 4158), the error “*The model is overloaded*” appeared with a 22.5% occurrence rate (tested around 9:00 UTC+1, which corresponds to working hours in Europe). Such an error rather relates to the performance of the LLM service provider, not the performance of the LLM-ExSys approach.

V. DISCUSSION

As an initial concept and implementation, LLM-ExSys has four limitations that should be further discussed as follows.

First, LLM-ExSys lacks a mechanism to ensure the consistency and correctness of rules and facts. Since knowledge engineers are no longer involved, the collaboration of multiple domain experts in an autonomous way may introduce errors or redundancies. To address this issue, one approach is to use an independent application or process, or assign a domain expert to periodically verify and clean the knowledge base. The verification can increase the cost, but is necessary for industrial-grade applications.

Second, non-deterministic responses occur when questions demand information not available in the knowledge base. A typical example of this issue is the fourth function presented in Section IV-C. To address this, LLM-ExSys can be deployed with a self-hosted fine-tuned LLM with domain-specific data. For example, in the case of RAASCEMAN, it is possible to fine-tune an LLM using a standardized product vocabulary, such as ECLASS, to ensure that all information about a queried product comes exclusively from this vocabulary. Another helpful approach is to guide the reasoning with stricter instructions to better frame its responses. For example, adding an instruction such as “*provide exactly 10 properties*” or specifying a selection rule such as “*choose the most common properties*” can improve clarity and focus in the output.

Third, data privacy issues arise when using LLM services without user data protection, such as the Google Gemini 2.5 Flash free tier. Three practical solutions can be considered: choosing a free-tier or paid-tier service that guarantees to protect user data, deploying a self-hosted LLM locally, and applying an LLM masking technique [12]. The first and second approaches inevitably require users to trade off data privacy against cost and performance. The third approach is about masking sensitive data before it is sent to the LLM service. This option mainly demands technical improvements; it is generally cheaper, but still requires additional efforts in LLM-ExSys deployment.

The fourth limitation relates the evaluation of the proof-of-concept system presented in Section IV-C. Since the number of test samples is quite small and there are no comparisons with other expert systems, this result can only demonstrate that new system architecture actually works. It does not provide a qualitative or quantitative assessment of its performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents an approach to use an LLM prompt engineering technique to enhance the expert system. LLM-powered expert systems support reduction of efforts and

involvement from knowledge engineers, by reducing the complexity, thus lowering costs. The LLM-ExSys developed as part of the ongoing RAASCEMAN project can not only support PDT development for the products defined in this project but also be extended to address other types of products. The expansion of the expert system to support additional products requires stronger evaluation frameworks for both LLMs and rule-based components.

Future works will focus on research topics such as trade-offs between latency and accuracy, as well as on applying adaptations like LoRA to locally deployed self-hosted fine-tuned LLMs to preserve organizational privacy. The fine-tuning also involves searching for suitable datasets or vocabularies about products and manufacturing. Moreover, LLM-ExSys will be subjected to a comprehensive stress test involving a larger set of test samples, diverse questions, and appropriate metrics.

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